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**TUPROQ QATQALOG'INI G'O'ZA NIXOLLARIGA TA'SIRI VA
UNI YUMSHATISHDA QO'LLANILADIGAN ESURSTEJAMKOR
MASHINALAR TAXLILI .**

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Annotatsiya. Maqola qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalashga asoslangan bo'lib, tuproqqa sayoz ishlov berish orqali dala dehqonchiligida yogingarchilikdan so'ng hosil bo'ladigan loyli qobiqni energiya va resurstejamkor qatqaloq yumshatgich agregatini qo'llash orqali yumshatib dehqonlarni og'irini engil qilishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'z: qatqaloq, texnik qurilma, texnologiya, agregat, yumshatuvchi barmoqlar.

Annotatsiya. The article is based on agricultural mechanization and aims to ease the burden on farmers by softening the silt shell formed after rainfall in field farming through shallow tillage using an energy and resource efficient silt softener unit.

Keywords: crust, technical device, technology, aggregate, softening fingers.

Абстракт. Статья основана на механизации сельского хозяйства, в полевом земледелии путем неглубокой обработки почвы глинистая корка, образующаяся после выщелачивания, смягчается за счет применения энергетического и ресурсосберегающего агрегата для выщелачивания твердых частиц.

Ключевые слова: корка, технический устройство, технология, агрегат, смягчительные палсы.

Erta bahorda yog'ingarchiliklarning talab etiladigan me'yoridan ortiq va surunkali yog'ishi tuproqda ortiqcha namlikni keltirib chiqaradi va etilishini kechiktiradi. Bunday holatlarda ekilgan chigitlar to'liq ko'karib chiqmaydi. Namlikni me'yoridan ortiq bo'lishi va havo haroratini birdaniga ko'tarilishi natijasida tuproqda qatqaloqlanish kuzatiladi.

Qatqaloq - kuchli yog'inlar va sug'orishdan so'ng tuproqda hosil bo'ladigan qattiq qatlam. O'rta Osiyoda sug'orma dehqonchilik iqlim tumanlarining deyarli barcha tuproqlari qatqaloqlanishga moyil.

1-rasm. Qatqaloqning unib chiqayotgan g' o'za ko'chatlariga ta'siri.

Kesaklarni maydalash, yaylovlar va quritilgan botqoqlarni bosish, tuproqni tekislash va zichlash, qatqaloqlarni buzish, mayda urug'larni ko'mishda g'altaklardan foydalaniladi.

G'altaklar tuproqni ekishga tayyorlash va ekishdan keyin ishlov berishda qo'llanilishi mumkin. G'altaklarni qo'llash orqali dala yuzasini ekishgacha tekislash, kesaklarni parchalash, qatqaloqni maydalash va asosiy ishlov berishdan keyingi joylashmagan tuproqni zichlashga erishiladi. G'altaklar ekishdan keyin tuproq yuqori qatlamni zichlab, urug'lar bilan bog'lanishini yaxshilaydi, buni natijasida urug'lar tezroq unib chiqadi [1].

2-rasm. G'altaklarning turlari.

a - tekis silindrik; b- tekis-qirrali; v- halqali-ponasimon; g – halqali-tishli; d – halqali-shporali (tepkili); e – boronasimon.

G'altaklar vazifasi bo'yicha dalabop yoki botqoqbop yuzasining shakli bo'yicha esa tekis silindrik, tekis chiziqli, halqali (ponasimon), halqali tishli, halqali tepkilli, boronasimon va xivichli g'altaklarga bo'linadi [2,3].

G'altaklar singari faol ta'sirli mashinalarga rotatsion tirmalar (motigalar) ni misol qilish mumkin. Rotatsion tirmalar (motigalar) quidagi: qatqaloqni parchalash, ekinzorlarga ishlov berish va angizni tirmalash ishlarida qo'llaniladi [4,5].

YUkoridagilarni inobatga olgan xolda quidagi rotatsion tirmani tavfsiya etiladi. Tavfsiya etilayotgan qurilma taqish moslamasi 1, qurilma ramasi 2 da bir-biriga nisbatan ma'lum masofada payvandlangan 8 ta ustun 3 lar, har bir ustunga erkin o'rnatilgan ikkita o'ng va chap tutkich 7 lar va unga yonlama o'rnatilgan to'g'ri tishli yumshatkich 4 lar o'rnatilgan [6,7]. O'ng va chap tutkichlar orasidagi masofani qator oralariga mos holda o'zgartirish uchun bir-biriga teleskopik kiritilgan tayanch 5 lar orqali, yumshatkichlarning ish jarayonida vertikal burchagini dala notekisligiga mos holda o'zgarishini ta'minlovchi prujinali mexanizm 6 tashkil topgan (3-rasm)[8,9].

3-rasm. Qatqaloqni yumshatish qurilmasining tuzilish sxemasi
Agregatni ishlatish texnologiyasiga to'xtaladigan bo'lsak, TTZ-80 traktoriga agregatlangan qurilma, rostlovchi tortqilar orqali gryadellarga ishlov berish uchun sozlanadi. Ishchi organi gryadelga parallelligi va erga tekis yotishini ta'minlanishi kerak aks holda ishlov berilgan dalani sifati yaxshi bo'lmaydi [10,11].

4-rasm. Qatqaloqni yumshatish qurilmasi ishchi organlarning ish jarayonida ko'rinishi.

Qurilma tishli yumshatkichi parametrlarini hisoblash uchun dastlabki

ma'lumotlar: qatqaloqning yumshatilish chuqurligi $h_{yu} = 0,04m = 4cm$, g'oz qator himoya zonasining kengligi $b_h = 0,1m = 10cm$, g'oz qatoridan tishli yumshatkichning tishigacha bo'lgan ko'ndalang masofa $l_k = 0,04m = 4cm$, sirpanish koeffitsienti $K_c = 0,2$ va kinematik parametri $\lambda = 0,8$.

Tishli yumshatkichning ko'ndalang-tik tekislikda gorizontga nisbatan o'rnatilish burchagini (1) ifoda orqali aniqlaymiz, ya'ni

$$\beta = \arctg \frac{h_{yu}}{b_h - l_k} = \arctg \frac{4}{10 - 4} = 33^\circ 42' \quad (1)$$

Demak, tishli yumshatkichning yumshatkichning ko'ndalang-tik tekislikda gorizontga nisbatan o'rnatilish burchagi $33-34^\circ$ ni tashkil etishi lozim [12,13].

Tishli yumshatkichning tuproqqa kirish chuqurligini (2) ifoda bo'yicha aniqlaymiz, ya'ni

$$h_k \geq \sqrt{(b_h - l_k)^2 + (h_{yu})^2} = \sqrt{(10 - 4)^2 + (4)^2} = 7,2 \text{ cm.} \quad (2)$$

Demak, tishli yumshatkichning tuproqqa kirish chuqurligi kamida 7 cm bo'lishi lozim [14].

Tishli yumshatkich tishining uzunligini (3) ifoda bo'yicha aniqlaymiz, ya'ni

$$l_t \geq \sqrt{(b_h - l_k)^2 + (h_{yu})^2} + l_q = \sqrt{(10 - 4)^2 + (4)^2} + 5 = 12,2 \text{ cm.} \quad (3)$$

Demak, tishli yumshatkich tishining uzunligi kamida 12 cm bo'lishi lozim [15].

Tishli yumshatkichning diametrini (4) ifoda bo'yicha aniqlaymiz, ya'ni

$$D \geq d_g + 2 \left[\sqrt{(b_h - l_k)^2 + (h_{yu})^2} + l_q \right] \cos \arctg \frac{h_{yu}}{b_h - l_k} = \\ = 8 + 2 \left[\sqrt{(10 - 4)^2 + (4)^2} + 5 \right] \cos \arctg \frac{4}{10 - 4} = 27,97 \text{ cm.} \quad (4)$$

Demak, tishli yumshatkichning diametri kamida 28 cm, radiusi esa kamida 14 cm bo'lishi lozim [16,17,18].

Ushbu qurilmani qo'llash orqali qatqaloqni yumshatilish jarayonida sarflanadigan metall, energiya va yoqilg'i sarfi kamaygan holda ish sifatini yaxshilantirishga erishiladi [19,20].

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